

Socio-Economic Transformations in Rehabilitated Tribal Societies: A Case Study Analysis

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Abstract:- Scheduled Tribal population belongs to socially weaker section of the society and they living in isolation from forward caste. They had poor living conditions. Even when majority of the communities in the world kept changing their life-styles, there are communities still living in line with their traditional values, customs and believes. Several factors have been identified for the slow progress of such groups. They are living under social and cultural backwardness, poor economic conditions, lack of education, and deficiency in infrastructural facilities, poor employment opportunities, and attitudes of main population towards men and so on. Rehabilitation plans in Kerala promised each eligible family that moved onto the farm a title deed of one acre land along with other facility which includes basic facility like drinking water, road, transportation, school, electricity and houses. Tribal communities are vulnerable even today not because they are poor, illiterate, asset less as compared to the general public but their vulnerability arises from their inability to cope and negotiate with the general public or with the mainstream economy society, culture and political system. The major significance of the study is to understand how the Government had rehabilitated the tribes and protect their rights and also provided efficient enmities to the tribe. The objectives of the study are to evaluate the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of rehabilitated tribal population. To understand the challenges faced by the rehabilitated tribes.

Keywords:- Tribals, Rehabilitation, Socio economic conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word "tribal" or Adivasi brings to our mind a picture of half-naked men and women, with arrows and spears in their hands, feathers in their heads, and speaking an indifferent language, and their lives often combined with a different ideology. Even when majority of the communities in the world kept changing their life-styles, there are communities still living in line with their traditional values, customs and believes. Several factors have been identified for the slow progress of such groups. They are living under social and cultural backwardness, poor economic conditions, lack of education, and deficiency in infrastructural facilities, poor employment opportunities, and attitudes of main population towards men and so on. There are around 36000 adivasis living in Kerala, southern India.

The dictionary meaning of rehabilitation is making fit a disabled or delinquent person a special treatment. Rehabilitation plans in Kerala promised each eligible family that moved onto the farm a title deed of one acre land along with other facility which includes basic facility like drinking water, road, transportation, school, electricity and houses. They were also to be provided with employment, financial assistance to start cultivation, Rs 3000 per person to build hut for immediate shelter as a temporary arrangements 1000to by tools for farming and also Rs 6 lakh to build proper house later. Along with these, there are also promises to distribute 10kg of rice each month for the rehabilitated tribal families. For year later some have managed to collect Rs 2000 from the authority. There are many hardest issues for the families at the village related with education, transport, health care etc. Many adivasis have conducted different form of struggle forgetting basic requirements from government and society of Kerala. Tribal communities are vulnerable even today not because they are poor, illiterate, asset less as compared to the general public but their vulnerability arises from their inability to cope and negotiate with the general public or with the mainstream economy society, culture and political system.

II. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Scheduled Tribal population belongs to socially weaker section of the society and they living in isolation from forward caste. They had poor living conditions. The major significance of the study is to understand how the Government had rehabilitated the tribes and protect their rights and also provided efficient enmities to the tribe. The objectives of the study are To evaluate the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of rehabilitated tribal population. To understand the challenges faced by the rehabilitated tribes.

III. METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data are used for the collection of data. Scheduled questionnaire is used for the study because most of them are illiterate and uneducated. On behalf of this observation method, field, study etc. may also employ to gather information from them. Secondary information, in the other hand, is collected from various sources. In order to collect the information we used various published and unpublished source like books, journals, magazine etc. are used.

IV. SELECTION OF THE AREA

District of Idukki in Kerala state is selected for the study. The Idukki district constituted 5.03% of tribal population in Kerala. The present study is for an understanding the rehabilitated tribe's socio economic condition of Mannamkandam village. Mannamkandam is a village in Adimaly where the Government has rehabilitated the tribes from different parts of the district according to their landlessness. Therefore the study area under the present topic was Mannamkandam and the colonies where the tribal families were rehabilitated.

The total rehabilitated colonies in Adimaly panchayath are 23 and the number of house hold in each colony is different. The 2 colonies are selected to the study. The sample households in this colony are selected through giving equal percentage of selection. From each colony 25 per cent of the household are decided to select for the study. The household are selected through convenience.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-Economic condition of Households and their Challenges Programme for the welfare of the society and economically backward people especially for the benefit of the scheduled tribes occupied a central position in the development plans of the state all the years. The geographical beauty of the place is very nice. The place is not much affected by any pollution. The households are kept very clean and not much affected by plastic or other wastes. By observation we can understand that their living condition is much better than other tribal colonies. This paper attempts to study the different aspects of socio-economic condition of respondents.

A. Type of family

Family is a basic unit of society, which assigns social status, roles and social responsibilities to every individual. Family is the most important and powerful institutions through which all values are developed over the period of time. Every individual attitudes and behaviour are moulded through this institution .In this sense, where the family is joint or nuclear family and it also determine the role of tribal families and their condition.

Table 1: Distribution of sample respondent according to the type of family

Sl. No	Type of family	Frequency	Percentage
1	Joint family	27	54
2	Nuclear	23	46
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

Field survey shows that 54 per cent of the tribal families are living in joint family and 46 per cent are living in nuclear family. Most of them living used to live together. Traditionally these communities are mostly living in joint family.

B. Age composition

The age composition of a population is important for several reasons. The population of children and older person has much to do with the balance of expenditure earning of income, disease etc. It also helps us to understand the old aged person and their earning, education of the children etc. The following table shows the age composition of the total household members.

Table 2: Classification of sample respondents on different Age composition

Sl. No	Age group	No of members	Percentage
1	0-6	14	5.6
2	7-14	30	12
3	15-35	80	32
4	36-60	76	30.4
5	Above 60	50	20
	Total	250	100

Source: field survey

The table no.2 reveals that 32 per cent of the members of the family is belonging to the age group of 15-35. Only a small number of members (5.6%) are belonging to the age group of 0-6.

C. Type of house

Food, shelter and cloth are the basic needs of the human being. Type of house is also an important element of socio-economic condition of the tribal. Traditionally they live in hut or kucha houses. Here the houses are provided by the Government as a part of rehabilitation. All the rehabilitated households are received pukka house as a part of

rehabilitation policy.They received concrete houses with two rooms. There is a small variation in the construction style in each colony .As a part of observation we can understand that their houses are better as compared to the other.The main shortage of house, as observed and told by some of the respondent is that of kitchen facility and toilet facility.Most of them cook at outside home.They make outside kitchen by bamboos and coconut leaf.

Beside this limitation they can live more safely in these houses. They cannot fear about rain and threats of animal. The Mannamkandam (Padikkappu) area is more affected by animals like elephant. We can see news related to the elephant attack on the agriculture lands of the tribes. The Government had provided such a houses with that they can sleep without fear.

D. Sanitation facility

The situation of sanitation facility is even worse in the tribal society in India. A society cannot progress unless its members progress and achieve refinement. Health plays a prominent role in achieving this goal. Healthy body harbours a healthy mind. Proper sanitation facility is needed to build a healthy society. In order to good health clean atmosphere is necessary. Every house should have sanitary latrines and drainage for the proper disposal of facial matters and waste water. For this toilet play a key role. The following table shows the condition of toilet facility.

Table 3: Distribution of household by sanitation facility

Sl no	Facility	Number of Household	Percentage
1	House with toilet	45	90
2	Without toilet	5	10
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

The table No.3 shows that about 90 percent of the households have sanitation facility. Only 10 per cent of the houses do not have toilet facility. This shows the condition of tribals were improved than previous. In this study shows in each houses have their own toilet facilities. The Government of India ensured toilet facilities of each tribal family. But some of them have still facing sanitation related issues. In the early times, they faces inadequate sanitation facility in every families. Now the panchayath and the tribal welfare fund provided the housing facility with toilet in each family.

E. Electricity

The empirical study shows that electricity consumption can achieve improved social development and faster economic growth. Now we are living technologically advanced world. Electricity plays a key role in this day to day life. Electricity helps to know outer information more quickly with the electrical equipment. The following table shows the number of household with the electrical equipment.

Table 4: Distribution of sample household according to electricity connection

Sl no	Mode	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Electrified	30	60
2	Unelectrified	20	40
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

The table No.4 reveals that 30 households of the total sample have been electrified that means 60 of the house hold are electrified. On the other hand 40 of the household are unelectrified houses. In the case of other colonies the things is different that is some household has connection and other have to give application for the connection. All the arrangements like wiring and all other maintenance work had already been done. There is all facility for the connection of electricity.

F. Educational status

Socio economic condition of the tribes is linked with the educational status of members. Elementary education is deemed to be free to all children but in practice it is not free due to several reasons. Firstly, the incentives schemes do not have full coverage and thus have limited value at community level. Secondly may of the benefit do not reach beneficiaries. Some of the major reason for the lack of education was poverty, lack of motivation and distance of the school etc. But tribal are offered to them.

The Kerala attended highest effective literacy. The literacy rate of scheduled tribes in Kerala is 51.09 per cent. Now a days the literacy rate among the tribe are increasing, parents send their child to the school for various purposes. The following table shows the educational status of the family members.

Table 5: Distribution of sample respondent on the basis of the present level of education

Sl no	Level of education	Number of members	Percentage
1	Illiterate	170	68
2	Primary	50	20
3	Upper primary	23	9.2
4	High school	7	2.8
5	Higher secondary	-	
6	Graduation	-	
7	Post-graduation	-	
8	Other	-	
Total		250	100

Source: field survey

The table No.5 shows the conditions of education among the sample respondents.68 per cent of the sample respondent are illiterate. There is no members completed high school and other higher level education. The government provides free and compulsory education. But people are not ready to go to school. They are not well aware about education. And tribal have long oral tradition. Their culture is oral. Their history myths and traditions are orally handed down from generation to generation. Most of the language does not have scripts of their own; their oral tradition still continues to exist. There is 20 per cent of the people have been in primary education and 9.2 per cent of the children are in the group of upper primary 2.8 per cent of

the children are in high school. Data shows that now a day the parents are more conscious about their children education. The Number of tribal children join in the school is increasing. School facility is available near the town. At the same time they have tribal school in Thodupuzha and there is also a hostel facility provided by Scheduled Caste development department.

G. Ration cards

A ration card is issued to any Indian who residing within the country.The Indian Government attempt to provide foods to the poor at subsidized rates and to assure them other nutritional benefits.

Table 6: Classification of household according to the availability of ration card

Sl.no	Condition	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Ration card	41	82
2	No ration card	9	18
Total		50	100

Source: survey data

The table No.6 shows that the household with ration card is 41 that is 82 per cent and house hold with no ration card is 9 and it is 18 per cent. Because they did not apply for the ration card. Ration card is essential for the tribal family who have no electricity. Because kerosene is the means for the light for the family. Through ration card they can buy essential commodities from public distribution centre.

H. Occupation

In the past majority of the tribal population lives in the forest or in the hilly areas. They had a primitive life style. Their occupation primarily confined to agriculture and other related activity. The occupational pattern of the tribal families are shown on the following table

Table 7: Distribution of sample respondent on the basis of jobs

Sl no	Jobs	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Coolie	60	54.54
2	Farm worker	2	1.81
3	Agriculture	46	41.81
4	Private Employee	2	1.81
5	Government employee	-	-
Total		110	100

Source: field survey

Table no.7 shows that out of the total members 54.54 per cent of the sample respondents are coolie workers. Only 2 people are private employee. Education is the most important base for Government jobs. Here most of the tribal members are illiterate they not even go to the school.Generally for any Government or high quality job requires a minimum qualification of matriculation. Lack of education is one of the most important problem for getting the job. Because of the problem of illiteracy they cannot be get good jobs from the public. The proportion of farm

workers is only 1.81 per cent.The major problem here is to find jobs.The Government has to provide necessary jobs for the tribes.The following figure shows the magnitude of the jobs under various heads.

I. Cultivation

Each rehabilitated family gets 1 acres of land as a part of the rehabilitation policy. This data had been collected to understand whether these lands are utilized or not. Whether they cultivate the land they can get food through that. The

following table shows how many of them fully utilize the land for the cultivation purpose.

Table 8: Classification of sample respondent on the mode of cultivation

Sl no	Mode	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Fully cultivating	32	64
2	A part is cultivating	16	32
3	No cultivation	2	4
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

In the sample respondent of 50 tribal family, 64 percentage of farmers are fully cultivated their land and 32 respondents are partly utilizing their land. The two families has no cultivation on their land. The major item of cultivation are Banana,tapioca,coffee plants cocoa etc.

J. Monthly income

In order to understand the living condition of the family, measurement of family income is very important. Majority of worker engaged in petty jobs or coolie works. They get only what is needed for their survival. By observation and field survey, we get the information that the coolie workers get job only for few days. Farm workers get job mostly.

Table 9: Distribution of sample household on the basis of their monthly income

Sl.No	Monthly Income	Number of Household	Percentage
1	1-500	2	4
2	500-1000	8	16
3	1000-1500	30	60
4	1500-3000	10	20
5	Above 3000	-	-
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

The table No.9 reveals that only 60 per cent of the tribals get monthly income of 1000-1500.This monthly income is gets from daily wage work. But they are not satisfied with this .Because they get only three or four work in a month. They buy essential things from ration shops. Some of them gets old age pension .Only 4 per cent of tribe gets Rs 500.

K. Asset ownership

Income also means amount derived from assets not only from job to which any members of the family can access. Tribal family possesses many assets as a means of income. The following table shows the no of family has different asset apart from land.

Table 10: Distribution of sample respondents according to the base of asset

Sl. No	Asset	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Having asset	15	30
2	No asset	35	70
Total			100

Source: Field Survey

The table No.10 shows that out of the 50 household 30 per cent of the house hold has asset like animal. At the same time 70 of the sample respondent do not owned any asset except the land received from the Government. Because they did not get any financial assistance to domesticate the animals. The major asset of the tribes is animal. They can earn money through this asset.

L. Health

Health is a pre-requisite for human development and is essentially concerned with the well-being of common man. The UNDP Human Development Index (HDI) comprises three components i.e health, education and income generating capacity. Health is a function, not only of medical care, but also of the integrated development of society –cultural, economic, educational, social and political. The health status of a society is intimately related to its value system, philosophical and cultural traditions, and

social, economic, and political organisation. Each of these aspects has a deep influence on health, which in turn influences all these aspects. The health and nutrition problems of the vast tribal population of India as are varied as the tribal groups as the tribal groups themselves who presented a bewildering diversity and variety in their socio-economic, socio-cultural and ecological settings. Therefore health is an important factor in the socio-economic conditions of the people. The table shows the health problem of tribals in this area.

Table 11: The household members having different diseases

Sl no	Name of disease	No of members
1	Malaria	-
2	Asthma	11
3	Kidney disease	2
4	Pneumonia	2
5	Other	90

Source: field survey

The table No.11 shows that the sample respondent had faced some disease like Asthma, Kidney disease, pneumonia and other diseases like frequent fever, cold, headache etc... which has been included in the category of others. Among the total number of members 11 members has asthma problem, 2 person had faces the kidney disease and other 2 faces the pneumonia.90 members has faces other petty diseases like fever etc. They have near hospital facility (Adimaly) to treat minor diseases but to treat major disease, they have to go kilometres. This is the challenge faced by the tribals in health sector.

M. Health insurance card

The Government of Kerala had taken up the Rashtriya Swasthya BimaYogana Scheme of Government of India along with health insurance scheme CHIS in 2008.The major objectives of this is to protect below poverty line household from the major health shocks that involve hospitalization. Health insurance card provide each household member a financial help when they are hospitalized due to major disease. It helps the tribal families to reduce their financial burden derived due to disease.

Table 12: Classification of sample respondent on the basis of health insurance card

Sl.No	Mode	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Have health insurance card	10	20
2	Have not	40	80
Total		50	100

Source: field survey

The table No.12 shows that the out of the total number of sample respondent the 20 per cent of the household have health insurance card and remaining 80 per cent of the sample respondent not. It is the Government agent's duty to ensure that all eligible people are gets the facility. The major reason behind this was the ignorance of the people. Some respondent even not heard about such facility.

N. Transport and communication facility

Transport and communication facility are the lifeline linking means for the tribals to outside the world. Mostly tribal areas are isolated from the main stream of the society. Traditionally they live in hilly areas and such people have

no connection with the outsiders. But now the situation has been changed. Technological and other development also take place in such area. Transportation facility is necessary for the people to make connection with the society. For the purpose to going hospital, higher education and marketing their product they require efficient transportation system. There are two bus services in this area. But to reach the tribal area we require other vehicles. Nearest town in this area is Irumbupalam. Jeep and auto facilities is more here.The other people also lives in the nearest area.

The following table shows the opinion of the sample respondent about the availability of transportation facility.

Table 13: Opinion of sample respondent about the transportation facility

Sl no	Opinion	Number of sample Respondent	Percentage
1	Very good	-	-
2	Good	5	10
3	Satisfactory	30	60
4	Worse	15	30

Source: field survey

The table No.13 reveals the condition of transportation facility 60 percent of the sampe respondent is satisfactory opinion about the present transportation facility. No sample respondent have says that the present transportation is very good.15 per cent of the sample respondent says that the present transportation facility is worse. Because there is no enough bus service in this area.

O. Communication facility

Communication facility is necessary to know or to receive outer information. Like transportation; communication is also play a linking activity with the tribal people to the society. In order to get information about what is happening to the society. We require communication and also we require various communication media

Table 14: Distribution of sample respondent according to the availability of communication Medias

Sl no	Media	Number of Household	Percentage
1	Television	30	60
2	Mobile phone	47	94
3	Radio	2	4
4	News paper	-	-

Source: field survey

The table no.14 shows the various communication media available to the sample respondent. Out of the 50 household 30 household have television facility. 47 families have mobile phone. Almost every family uses the mobile phones. Out of 50 only 2 families have Radio .No household buy newspaper.

P. Responses towards the facility

Government has the responsibility to provide efficient facility to the vulnerable group for the development of the economy. The Government had agreed to provide all the amenities to the rehabilitated tribes. Their responses is that, improves their living condition compare than before. The following table shows the responses of the sample respondent about the various facility received by them.

Table 15: Responses of sample respondent (in percent)

Sl no		Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage
1	Are you satisfied with the housing facility received from the government?	40	80	10	20
2	Are you satisfied with the hospital facility?	46	92	4	8
3	Are you feeling any improvement in living condition after reach here?	50	100	0	0
4	Did you think that whether your culture have been effected by the rehabilitation	16	32	34	68

Source: field survey

The table No.15 shows the response of sample respondent towards the various facility received by the sample household. In the case of housing facility 40 per cent are satisfied with the facility; in the case of hospital facility 46 are satisfied. The response of sample respondent towards their cultural change reveals that rehabilitation does not affect their culture much. By considering overall living condition they say that their living condition is much better after reached here. At the same time they require some more facility of improvement in the existing facility.

VI. CHALLENGES FACED BY THE REHABILITATED TRIBES

Through this analysis of socio economic conditions of household, we can also found some challenges. Most of the tribes gets adequate facilities like sanitation, proper housing, Health and insurance card etc. But few of them left for the proper facilities especially in the case of housing that we already discussed in the above section. They did not have strong roofs in their house. During the rainy season they face serious issues and each rainy season is the fear in their mind. In the case of electricity and communication facilities same situation are there. In the case of income distribution and employment opportunity, they did not get enough job, and income to satisfy their needs. Some respondent responds, they only get two or three work in a month. Welfare means we can simply call it as the good effects should enjoy the whole community or each and every people. Then only the welfare is possible. If the 90 per cent of tribes is ok with the facility and the other 10 is facing serious issue means that is not the good welfare. The government provides welfare fund for the tribal people, But the local authority does not check properly whether it is

come up to every hand or not. That is the reason behind the poor condition of the 10 per cent.

VII. CONCLUSION

Rehabilitation is an action by the Government in which the landless people are transplanted from their existing location to a new atmosphere. Mannamkandam village is such an area where the landless tribal had resettled by the government during 1950 onwards. It is concluded from the study undertaken that their socio economic condition is much better as compared to their past condition. The study reveals that their housing condition is little better than other such vulnerable group. Now the socio economic condition of the rehabilitated tribes is much more improved. By giving special attention on providing all house hold the availability of employment opportunity, electricity and other facility their condition can be improved.

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